

Geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory in spherically symmetric curved space-time

Miftachul Hadi,^{1,2} Nuryani,³ and Suhadi Mulyono⁴

¹*Badan Riset dan Inovasi Nasional (BRIN), KST Habibie (Puspiptek), Gd 442, Serpong, Tangerang Selatan 15314, Banten, Indonesia.*

²*Institute of Mathematical Sciences, Kb Kopi, Jalan Nuri I, No.68, Pengasinan, Gn Sindur 16340, Bogor, Indonesia. E-mail: instmathsci.id@gmail.com*

³*Physics Department, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Jl. Ir. Sutami 36A, Surakarta 57126, Jawa Tengah, Indonesia.*

⁴*Jurusan Fisika FMIPA, Universitas Mulawarman, Jalan Barong Tongkok, Gn. Kelua, Samarinda Ulu 75242, Samarinda, Kalimantan Timur, Indonesia.*

We treat geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory the same as Maxwell's theory. This treatment has consequences in that we have the concepts of phase (eikonal), gauge potential, and field strength tensor in geometrical optics as in Maxwell's theory. We formulate the eikonal equation (the equation which describes the light ray propagation) of geometrical optics in (3+1)-dimensional spherically symmetric curved space-time using the gauge (vector) potential related to Clebsch variables, scalar variables. These Clebsch variables are related to any divergenceless vector field where the divergenceless property of any vector field means that there is no source to give rise to such a vector field. We assume that the electromagnetic fields (the set of the solutions of Maxwell equations) consist of the subset fields, scalar fields. These scalar fields have isotropic (well-defined) properties, i.e. they are defined for an infinite distance (radius) from the origin or the source, so that the direction does not matter. The components of the subset fields are related to Clebsch variables. These subset fields satisfy the non-linear field theory but the electromagnetic fields do not. In the case of a weak field, the non-linear field theory reduces to Maxwell's linear theory. We assume also that spherically symmetric curved space-time is the same as empty space-time consisting of the spherically symmetric gravitational weak field described by the Schwarzschild metric. The propagation of the ray follows the null geodesic. The treatment of the electromagnetic fields consisting of the subset fields has far-reaching consequences related to topology.

Keywords: *geometrical optics, $U(1)$ local gauge theory, eikonal equation, subset field, weak field, spherically symmetric curved space-time.*

I. INTRODUCTION

What is the very interesting view in geometrical optics? Why could geometrical optics be treated as an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory? Geometrical optics is a simplified theory than the electromagnetic wave of Maxwell's theory to describe the behaviour of light. Geometrical optics corresponds to the limiting case of a very small wavelength of light, $\lambda \rightarrow 0$ ^{1,2}, in comparison with the characteristic dimension of the problem³ i.e. the system with which light interacts⁴ or to each of the other scales present (the scale of observation⁵), so that the electromagnetic waves can be regarded locally as plane waves propagating through space-time⁶. Geometrical optics employs the concept of rays, which are defined as the direction of the energy propagation in the limit of a very small wavelength of light⁴. The fact that a very small wavelength of light in comparison with the scale of observation is called the classical limit⁷.

As an example geometrical optics is a simplified theory than the electromagnetic wave, we can observe the spreading of light due to diffraction entirely because of the finiteness of the wavelength. However, if we assume that the wavelength tends to zero then we can perform the infinitesimally thin beam of light that defines rays⁴.

It is commonly considered that $U(1)$ local gauge theory

describes Maxwell's theory. One of the reasons that geometrical optics could be treated as $U(1)$ local gauge theory is that geometrical optics (the eikonal equation) can be derived from Maxwell's equations^{4,8,9} where Maxwell's theory is $U(1)$ local gauge theory where rays are invariant under a local gauge transformation¹⁰. This view of geometrical optics as a gauge theory, in turn, could be related to topological field theory where geometrical optics could have a topological structure.

It is rare to find articles that discuss geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory^{6,11-13}. Geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory in (3+1)-dimensional curved space-time had been considered^{11,12}. There¹² the electromagnetic wave or light ray propagation had been formulated as the dispersion relation from which the eikonal-type equation can be reconstructed. They^{6,11,12} say nothing about the electromagnetic field (a set of solutions of Maxwell equations) could be treated as a set of subset fields.

In this article, we propose geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory in (3+1)-dimensional curved space-time using a scalar field as a subset field. Especially, we formulate the eikonal equation, the equation which describes the light rays propagation, in (3+1)-dimensional curved space-time using the gauge potential related to Clebsch (scalar) variables. We assume that curved space-

time is the same as empty space-time where there is no matter present and there are no physical fields except the gravitational field which does not disturb the emptiness (other fields disturb the emptiness)¹⁴. Curved or empty space-time is described by the Schwarzschild metric and ray propagation obeys the null geodesic. To the best of our knowledge, the formulation of the eikonal equation in (3+1)-dimensional spherically symmetric curved space-time using the gauge potential related to Clebsch variables has not been done yet.

II. $U(1)$ GAUGE THEORY

Maxwell's theory is well known as $U(1)$ local gauge theory. The treatment of geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory implies that we have the concept of gauge potential in geometrical optics in the same form as the gauge potential in Maxwell's theory. Such gauge potential can be written as

$$\vec{A}_\mu = \vec{a}_\mu(\vec{r}, t) e^{iq(\vec{r}, t)} \quad (1)$$

where \vec{A}_μ is a complex^{6,15} gauge potential, $\vec{a}_\mu(\vec{r}, t)$ is a complex amplitude⁶, a slowly varying function of space coordinates and time³, $q(\vec{r}, t)$ is the eikonal (a real phase⁶), $e^{iq(\vec{r}, t)}$ is a complex scalar function. \vec{A}_μ as \vec{a}_μ can be interpreted as the oscillating variable¹⁶, the displacement from an equilibrium¹⁷ (an equilibrium is a position at infinity where the gauge potential can be assumed equal to zero).

As $U(1)$ local gauge theory, the related field strength tensor of Maxwell's theory in (3+1)-dimensional space-time can be written as

$$\vec{F}_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \vec{A}_\nu - \partial_\nu \vec{A}_\mu \quad (2)$$

where $\partial_\mu, \partial_\nu$ denote the partial derivatives (four-gradient), μ, ν denote four coordinates of space-time i.e. three-dimensional space plus one-dimensional time, \vec{A}_ν, \vec{A}_μ are the gauge potentials. The same gauge potential and its related field strength tensor for geometrical optics.

III. EIKONAL AND PHASE IN GEOMETRICAL OPTICS

What is an eikonal in geometrical optics? Why is the eikonal, especially the phase, very important? In the case of a steady (unchanging in time) monochromatic wave, the frequency¹⁸ is constant and the time dependence of the phase, $q(\vec{r}, t)$, is given by a term $-f_\theta t$ (we can write it as $\partial q / \partial t = -f_\theta$) where f_θ denotes (angular) frequency³. We see that the phase is an angle (in radians or degrees).

The relation between the eikonal, $\psi(\vec{r})$, and the phase can be written as³

$$\psi(\vec{r}) = \frac{c}{f_\theta} q(\vec{r}, t) + ct \quad (3)$$

where ψ is a function of space coordinates only³, "a length" of line in space, a real¹⁹ scalar function and c is the speed of light (a scalar) in vacuum (in our context is flat) space. The phase can be written explicitly from eq.(3) as

$$q(\vec{r}, t) = X(\psi - ct) \quad (4)$$

where $X = f_\theta / c$.

IV. ELECTROMAGNETIC FIELD AND ITS SUBSET FIELD

Let us assume that the electromagnetic fields (the set of the solutions of Maxwell equations) consist of subset fields²⁰, scalar fields, $\phi(\vec{r}, t)$, function of space-time. Any electromagnetic field is locally equal to a subset field i.e. any electromagnetic field can be obtained by patching together subset fields (except in a zero-measure set) but globally different²⁰. This means that the difference between the set of the subset fields and all the electromagnetic fields in Maxwell's theory in flat space-time is global instead of local since the subset fields obey the topological quantum condition²⁰ but the electromagnetic fields do not.

The electromagnetic field satisfies a linear field equation, but a subset field satisfies a non-linear field equation. Both fields, the electromagnetic field as a set and its subset field, satisfy the linear field equation in the case of the weak field²¹. In other words, the vacuum Maxwell's theory is the weak-field limit²¹ of a non-linear subset field theory. It means that a non-linear subset field theory reduces to the vacuum Maxwell's linear theory in the case of the weak field. What we mean with the weak field is $|\phi\phi^*| \ll 1$ where ϕ^* is the complex conjugate of ϕ .

As a consequence that the electromagnetic fields in flat space-time have a subset field, a scalar field, a function of space-time with all of its properties, we also have such a subset field in geometrical optics which can be written as

$$\phi(\vec{r}, t) = \rho(\vec{r}, t) e^{iq(\vec{r}, t)} \quad (5)$$

and

$$f(\vec{r}, t) = -1/[2\pi(1 + \rho^2)] \quad (6)$$

where $\rho(\vec{r}, t)$ is the amplitude, a slowly varying function of the coordinates and time³, $q(\vec{r}, t)$ is the phase, $f(\vec{r}, t)$ is the function of amplitude. The treatment (5) is based on the wave point of view of the field. We could interpret the scalar field as the disturbance where the physical disturbance is the real part of a scalar field²². We call the functions, $q(\vec{r}, t)$ (5) and $f(\vec{r}, t)$ (6), as the Clebsch variables²³ or Gaussian potentials²⁴. These Clebsch variables are related to any divergenceless vector field²⁰. The divergenceless property of any vector field means that there is no source to give rise to such a vector field. An example of a divergenceless vector field is the magnetic

field \vec{B} , where $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$. It has a consequence that $\vec{B} = \nabla \times \vec{A}$, where \vec{A} is potential. The Clebsch variables are not uniquely defined. However, many different choices are possible for them²⁰.

By using the Clebsch variables, f and q ²³, the field strength tensor of the geometrical optics, eq.(2), can be written as²³

$$\vec{F}_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu(f \partial_\nu q) - \partial_\nu(f \partial_\mu q) \quad (7)$$

The eqs.(2), (7) are the linear field equations.

By observing the equality of eqs.(2) and (7), we see that²³

$$\vec{A}_\nu = f \partial_\nu q, \quad \vec{A}_\mu = f \partial_\mu q \quad (8)$$

Eq.(8) shows that the gauge (vector) potential can be written using the Clebsch (scalar) variables. Understanding a scalar is simpler than a vector. This is one of the reasons why we use the Clebsch variables.

V. EIKONAL EQUATION IN 3-DIMENSIONAL EUCLIDEAN SPACE

Let us review in brief the eikonal equation in 3-dimensional Euclidean space and (3+1)-dimensional Minkowskian space-time. In 3-dimensional Euclidean (flat) space, \mathbb{R}^3 , the equation of ray²⁵ propagation in a transparent medium²⁶ can be written as^{3,9,27,28}

$$|\vec{\nabla}\psi(x, y, z)| = |\vec{n}(x, y, z)| = n(x, y, z), \quad (9)$$

$$x, y, z \in \Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3$$

subject to $\psi(x, y, z)|_{\partial\Omega} = 0$ means that the solution, $\psi(x, y, z)$, at the boundary, $\partial\Omega$, is equal to zero, Ω is an open set²⁷, bounded²⁹, with suitably smooth (well-behaved) boundary²⁷ in 3-dimensional Euclidean space, $|\cdot|$ denotes the Euclidean norm²⁸, a distance function, $\vec{\nabla}$ denotes the gradient, $n(x, y, z)$ is the refractive index, a dimensionless quantity, a real scalar function of coordinates with positive values, the slowness at a point, (x, y, z) , lies inside Ω ²⁷. The refractive index is typically supplied as known input, given, and we seek the solution, $\psi(x, y, z)$, the shortest time needed to travel from a point, (x, y, z) , to the boundary, $\partial\Omega$ ²⁷.

VI. EIKONAL EQUATION IN (3+1)-DIMENSIONAL MINKOWSKIAN SPACE-TIME

In $(3 + 1)$ -dimensional Minkowskian (flat, pseudo-Euclidean¹) space-time, the gradient operator in eq.(9), $\vec{\nabla}$, is replaced by the covariant four-gradient, ∂_μ . The same also applies to ∂_ν . So, eq.(9) becomes

$$|\partial_\mu\psi(x, y, z)| = n(x, y, z) \quad (10)$$

where μ runs from 1 to 3+1 by considering that the time derivative of ψ is equal to zero. The eikonal equation (10)

describes the propagation of wavefronts (field discontinuities) in (3+1)-dimensional Minkowskian space-time³⁰.

We see from eq.(10), that the zeroth rank tensor (a scalar) of the refractive index describes an isotropic linear optics³¹. It means that flat space-time describes an isotropic linear optics³². But, the refractive index can also be e.g. a second rank tensor which describes the electric field component along one axis may be affected by the electric field component along another axis³³. The second rank tensor of the refractive index describes an anisotropic linear optics³¹.

By multiplying \vec{A}_ν in eq.(8) with f^* , i.e. the conjugate complex of f , we obtain

$$\vec{A}_\nu f^* = f \partial_\nu q f^* = f f^* \partial_\nu q \quad (11)$$

where $f f^*$ is a scalar (a number). To simplify the problem, we can take $f f^* = 1$ then eq.(11) becomes

$$f \partial_\nu q f^* = \frac{\partial q}{\partial x^\nu} \quad (12)$$

Multiply both side of eq.(12) with dx^ν and do integration for both sides then we obtain

$$\int f \partial_\nu q f^* dx^\nu = q \quad (13)$$

The same way applies to A_μ (8). We obtain

$$\int f \partial_\mu q f^* dx^\mu = q \quad (14)$$

Eqs.(13), (14) are the explicit equations that relate the phase and the $U(1)$ gauge potential written using the Clebsch variables.

By substituting eq.(13) into eq.(3), we obtain

$$\psi = \frac{c}{f_\theta} \int f \partial_\nu q f^* dx^\nu + ct \quad (15)$$

and by substituting eq.(15) into eq.(10), we obtain

$$\left| \partial_\mu \left\{ \frac{c}{f_\theta} \int f \partial_\nu q f^* dx^\nu + ct \right\} \right| = n \quad (16)$$

Eq.(16) shows explicitly the relation between the $U(1)$ gauge potential which represents the existence of the light and the refractive index, a ratio of the light propagation in flat space-time and medium. In the case of medium is flat space-time, the refractive index in eq.(16) can be replaced by a number, 1. It means that the light ray trajectory is a straight line.

VII. EIKONAL EQUATION IN (3+1)-DIMENSIONAL SPHERICALLY SYMMETRIC CURVED SPACE-TIME

Let us consider the light rays trajectory (16) for the light rays propagating through curved or empty space-time, i.e. medium of the field of gravitation described by the simplest metric, the Schwarzschild metric. Roughly

speaking, the metric is an interval of space-time. The Schwarzschild metric assumes curved space-time of the static spherically symmetric gravitational field due to a mass of the spherically symmetric body at rest¹⁴.

Why do we formulate geometrical optics in curved space-time? One of the interesting reasons is that there exists a phenomenon in the universe, especially in cosmology, where light propagates through curved space-time (this phenomenon is known as a gravitational lensing³⁴) and behaves as if light rays in geometrical optics were traversing an inhomogeneous medium³⁴. An inhomogeneous medium here is analogous to curved space-time (space-time with a gravitational field).

The static spherically symmetric gravitational field described by the Schwarzschild metric³⁵ can be written as

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right) c^2 dt^2 + \left(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi \quad (17)$$

where $r_s = 2GM/c^2$ is the Schwarzschild radius, M is the mass of the spherically symmetric body (a constant of integration¹⁴, a number^{36,37}), G is the gravitational constant, c is the speed of light, r is the spatial (radial) coordinate. Equation (17) is also known as the Schwarzschild solution¹⁴. The Schwarzschild solution (the Schwarzschild metric) holds outside the surface of the massive body that is producing the gravitational field, where there is no matter¹⁴.

The world line corresponding to the propagation of light is described by a null geodesic (the track of a null vector¹⁴) as written below

$$ds^2 = 0 \quad (18)$$

A null geodesic (18) in curved space-time is a generalization of a null interval (a null distance) in a flat space-time. Both are the consequence of the invariance of the speed of light observed by inertial and non-inertial frames of reference where the locality applies. Two points that do not coincide and are located on the null geodesic, the space-time distance between them is zero and so the tangent line is perpendicular to itself³⁸.

By substituting eq.(18) into eq.(17) and using relations $dr/dt = v$, $c/v = n$, assume that θ and ϕ are constant and rearrange the terms, we obtain the space-dependent refractive index as written below^{39,40}

$$n(r) = \left(1 - \frac{2G}{c^2 r} M\right)^{-1} \quad (19)$$

We see from eq.(19) that the refractive index is related to the mass of the spherically symmetric body.

By substituting eq.(19) into eq.(16), we obtain the eikonal equation in (3+1)-dimensional spherically symmetric curved space-time as below

$$\left| \partial_\mu \left\{ \frac{c}{f_\theta} \int f \partial_\nu q f^* dx^\nu + ct \right\} \right| = \left(1 - \frac{2G}{c^2 r} M\right)^{-1} \quad (20)$$

Eq.(20) shows explicitly the relation between the mass of the spherically symmetric body that is producing the

spherically symmetric gravitational field and the $U(1)$ gauge potential which represents the existence of the light rays. The refractive index as a function of mass (not equal to 1) has a consequence that the light ray trajectory is bending due to the light ray following the "straight path" of the spherically symmetric curved space-time.

As we have mentioned, the refractive index is typically supplied as known input, given, and we seek the solution, the eikonal. In the case of cosmology, the problem becomes more realistic and very interesting if we consider e.g. the mass of black holes as known input. How about the behaviour of the light ray if it propagates through a near black hole, an event horizon?

VIII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The treatment of geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory has consequences in that we have the concepts of phase (eikonal), gauge potential and field strength tensor in geometrical optics as in Maxwell's theory. The importance of phase is that the values of gauge potential, field strength tensor, and in turn energy of the physical system are not changing as we change phase by gauge (phase) transformation. It differs from other components of gauge potential, e.g. amplitude. The energy of the physical system we observe changes if we change amplitude. The treatment of geometrical optics as gauge theory has the consequence that it is possible to investigate the symmetrical properties of geometrical optics.

The property of a scalar field is isotropic (well-defined) for an infinite distance (radius) from the origin or the source. The infinite radius from the source implies the isotropic space-time where the direction does not matter. It is in harmony with the property of space-time (geometry). A space-time could be locally anisotropic but globally isotropic (the distribution of matter energy in the universe is assumed to be homogeneous). Any space that is isotropic about every point is also homogeneous³².

The assumption that the set of the solutions of Maxwell equations has subset fields (consisting of scalar fields written using the Clebsch variables) has far-reaching consequences. The Clebsch variables are related to any divergenceless vector field²⁰. The divergenceless property of any vector field means that there is no source to give rise to such a vector field. An example of a divergenceless vector field is the magnetic field \vec{B} , where $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$. It has a consequence that $\vec{B} = \nabla \times \vec{A}$, where \vec{A} is potential. The Clebsch variables are not uniquely defined. However, many different choices are possible for them²⁰. In analogy with the hydrodynamics, velocity (vector) field and (vector) vorticity of the fluid helicity can also be written using the Clebsch variables²⁴. Velocity field and vorticity are identical to gauge potential and field strength tensor, respectively. The role of the Clebsch variables is significant for understanding the topological features of the fluid flow where the fluid helicity could be interpreted as a knot⁴¹ through Chern-Simons

topological field theory.

We could say that the eqs.(13), (15), (16) are new formulations of the phase, the eikonal, the eikonal equation, respectively, written using the Clebsch (scalar) variables. It might be possible that we could consider the light ray trajectory described by the eikonal equation to be identical to the fluid flow. The eikonal equation is a type of the first order non-linear partial differential equation^{27,42,43}, an approximated version of the wave equation⁴⁴, a typical example of steady-state Hamilton-Jacobi equations^{45,46}. The eikonal equation can be derived from Fermat's principle⁴⁷, the Euler-Lagrange equation⁴⁷, and Maxwell equations^{9,27,48}. We consider that the nonlinearity of the eikonal equation is due to a non-linear property of its Euclidean norm⁴⁹.

The Schwarzschild metric as the solution of Einstein field equation assumes a static spherically symmetric gravitational field. If spherical symmetry is assumed, the Einstein field equation can be solved for a collapsing star rather explicitly and show that the formation of a singularity is unavoidable⁵⁰. But what happens if the geometry is not quite spherically symmetric⁵⁰?

Eq.(20) shows explicitly the relation between the mass of the spherically symmetric body that is producing the spherically symmetric gravitational field and the $U(1)$ gauge potential which represents the existence of the light rays. The refractive index as a function of mass (not equal to 1) has a consequence that the light ray trajectory is bending due to light ray following the "straight path" of the spherically symmetric curved space-time. In the case of cosmology, the problem becomes more realistic and very interesting if we consider e.g. the mass of black holes as known input. How about the behaviour of the light ray if it propagates through a near black hole, an event horizon? Does the light ray trajectory make a closed loop, a knot?

IX. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to thank Professor Hishamuddin Zainuddin, Richard Tao Roni Hutagalung, Andri Sofyan Hussein, Fiki Taufik Akbar, Idham Syah Alam, Handhika Satrio Ramadhan, Johan Matheus Tuwankotta, Lalu Zam, Chrisna Setyo Nugroho, AI (Chat GPT) for comments and fruitful discussions. Also we would like to thank the Reviewers for reviewing this manuscript.

MH thanks to Juwita Armilia and Aliya Syauqina Hadi for much love. Al Fatihah for his Ibunda and Ayahanda. May Allah bless them Jannatul Firdaus.

This research is supported fully by self-funding.

¹L. D. Landau, E. M. Lifshitz, *The Classical Theory of Fields*, Pergamon Press, 1994.

²The distance between two nearest points in the plane wave having the same phase is equal to a wavelength. In other words, the planes in the plane waves represents the wavefront, spaced a wavelength apart (see David Halliday, Robert Resnick, *Fundamentals of Physics*, John Wiley & Sons, 1976).

- ³L. D. Landau, E. M. Lifshitz, *Electrodynamics of Continuous Media*, Pergamon Press, 1984.
- ⁴A .K. Ghatak, K. Thyagarajan, *Contemporary Optics*, Plenum Press, 1978.
- ⁵Ramamurti Shankar, *Fundamental of Physics II: Electromagnetism, Optics, and Quantum Mechanics*, Yale University Press, 2016.
- ⁶Charles W. Misner, Kip S. Thorne, John Archibald Wheeler, *Gravitation*, W.H. Freeman and Company, 1973, p.573.
- ⁷L. D. Landau, E. M. Lifshitz, *Quantum Electrodynamics*, Elsevier Ltd, 1982.
- ⁸Arnold Sommerfeld, *Optics. Lectures on Theoretical Physics. Volume IV*, Academic Press, 1949.
- ⁹Max Born, Emil Wolf, *Principles of Optics*, Pergamon Press, 1993.
- ¹⁰J. L. Synge, *Geometrical Mechanics and de Broglie Waves*, Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- ¹¹Alexander B. Balakin, Alexei E. Zayats, Non-minimal Einstein- Maxwell theory: the Fresnel equation and the Petrov classification of a trace-free susceptibility tensor, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1710.08013.pdf>.
- ¹²A. B. Balakin, A. E. Zayats, *Ray Optics in the Field of a Non-minimal Dirac Monopole*, Gravitation and Cosmology, 2008, Vol. 14, No. 1, pp. 86-94.
- ¹³Miftachul Hadi, Suhadi Mulyono, *Geometrical optics as an Abelian $U(1)$ gauge theory in a vacuum space-time*, Indonesian Physical Review, vol. 7, no. 1, p 143-151, 2024 and all references therein. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.29303/ipr.v7i1.278>
- ¹⁴P. A. M Dirac, *General Theory of Relativity*, John Wiley & Sons, 1975.
- ¹⁵Dimitar Simeonov, *On some properties of the electromagnetic field and its interaction with a charged particle*, 2020, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2004.09273.pdf>.
- ¹⁶Wikipedia, *Amplitude*.
- ¹⁷H. J. Pain, *The Physics of Vibrations and Waves*, John Wiley & Sons, 1983.
- ¹⁸The time derivative of phase, q , gives the angular frequency of the wave, $\partial q/\partial t = -f_\theta$ and the space derivatives of q gives the wave vector, $\vec{\nabla}q = \vec{k}$, which shows the direction of the ray propagation through any point in space (see L. D. Landau, E. M. Lifshitz, *Electrodynamics of Continuous Media*, Pergamon Press, 1984).
- ¹⁹The complex eikonal equation in a 3-dimensional space where the eikonal, ψ , is treated as a complex scalar field is considered (see A. Wereszczynski, *Knots, Braids and Hedgehogs from the Eikonal Equation*, 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/math-ph/0506035v1.pdf>).
- ²⁰Antonio F Ranada, *Topological electromagnetism*, J. Phys. A: Math. Gen. **25** (1992) 1621-1641.
- ²¹Antonio F. Ranada, *A Topological Theory of the Electromagnetic Field*, Letters in Mathematical Physics **18**: 97-106, 1989.
- ²²J. F. Nye, *Natural Focusing and Fine Structure of Light*, IOP Publishing Ltd, 1999.
- ²³A. F. Ranada, A. Tiemblo, *A Topological Structure in the Set of Classical Free Radiation Electromagnetic Fields*, arXiv:1407.8145v1 [physics.class-ph] 29 Jul 2014.
- ²⁴Roman Jackiw, *Lectures on Fluid Dynamics*, Springer, 2002.
- ²⁵Rays are the straight line paths followed by narrow beams of light (J.O. Bird, *Light rays*, ScienceDirect Topics). A line normal to the wavefronts, indicating the direction of motion of the waves, is called a ray (David Halliday, Robert Resnick, *Fundamentals of Physics*, John Wiley & Sons, 1976).
- ²⁶Only transparent media are considered in the geometrical optics (L.D. Landau, E.M. Lifshitz, *Electrodynamics of Continuous Media*, Pergamon Press, 1984).
- ²⁷Wikipedia, *Eikonal Equation*.
- ²⁸The Euclidean distance of a vector from the origin is a norm, called the Euclidean norm, or 2-norm, which may also be defined as the square root of the inner product of a vector with itself. The absolute value $\|x\| = |x|$ is a norm on the one-dimensional vector spaces formed by the real or complex numbers (Wikipedia,

- Norm (mathematics)*).
- ²⁹Jinghong Miao, *Viscosity solutions of the eikonal equations*, 2020, <http://math.uchicago.edu/~may/REU2020/REUPapers/Miao,Jinghong.pdf>.
- ³⁰C. Adam, *Hopf maps as static solutions of the complex eikonal equation*, 2004, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/math-ph/0312031.pdf>.
- ³¹Roniyus Marjunus, *Private communication*.
- ³²Steven Weinberg, *Gravitation and Cosmology*, John Wiley & Sons, 1972, p.379.
- ³³Karsten Rottwitt, Peter Tidemand-Lichtenberg, *Nonlinear Optics: Principles and Applications*, CRC Press, 2015.
- ³⁴Eugene Hecht, *Optics*, Addison-Wesley, 2002.
- ³⁵Jim Branson, *The Schwarzschild Metric*, https://hepweb.ucsd.edu/ph110b/110b_notes/node75.html, 2012.
- ³⁶Wikipedia, *Constant of integration*.
- ³⁷The constant of integration can be a real or a complex numbers <https://www.quora.com/Is-the-constant-of-integration-a-natural-number> <https://www.researchgate.net/post/Is-constant-of-integration-real-or-complex>.
- ³⁸Hans. J. Wospakrik, *Berkenalan dengan Teori Kerelatifan Umum Einstein*, Penerbit ITB, 1987.
- ³⁹Miftachul Hadi, *A refractive index of a kink in curved space*, 2019, <https://intra.lipi.go.id/public/uploads/kegiatan/2019/1609335835.pdf>.
- ⁴⁰Soma Mitra, Somenath Chakrabarty, *Fermat's Principle in Curved Space-Time, No Emission from Schwarzschild Black Hols as Total Internal Reflection and Black Hole Unruh Effect*, 2015, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1512.03885.pdf>.
- ⁴¹Miftachul Hadi, *Knot in geometrical optics*, and all references therein, 2022, <https://vixra.org/abs/2207.0114>. Miftachul Hadi, *Knot in weak-field geometrical optics*, and all references therein, 2023, <https://osf.io/e7afj/>.
- ⁴²Pavel Mokry, *Iterative method for solving the eikonal equation*, Proceedings Volume 10151, Optics and Measurement International Conference 2016; 101510Z (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2257326>.
- ⁴³Science Direct, *Eikonal Equation*, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/eikonal-equation>.
- ⁴⁴Rafael G Gonzalez-Acuna, Hector A Chaparro-Romo, *Stigmatic Optics*, IOP Publishing Ltd, 2020.
- ⁴⁵Alexander G. Churbanov, Petr N. Vabishchevich, *Numerical solution of boundary value problems for the eikonal equation in an anisotropic medium*, arXiv:1802.06203v1 [cs.NA] 17 Feb 2018, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1802.06203.pdf>.
- ⁴⁶See Wikipedia, *Symplectomorphism*; Proofwiki.org, *Isomorphism preserves commutativity*.
- ⁴⁷S. Cornbleet, *On the eikonal function*, Radio Science, Volume 31, Number 6, Pages 1697-1703, November-December 1996.
- ⁴⁸Consuelo Bellver-Cebreros, Marcelo Rodriguez-Danta, *Eikonal equation from continuum mechanics and analogy between equilibrium of a string and geometrical light rays*, Am. J. Phys. **69** (3), March 2001.
- ⁴⁹ScienceDirect, *Euclidean Norm*.
- ⁵⁰Edward Witten, *Light rays, singularities, and all that*, Reviews of Modern Physics, Volume 92, October-December 2020.